

IMPORTANCE OF BODY LANGUAGE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article discusses how to use body language in English lessons and its value, as well as the secrets of nonverbal communication and useful special strategies that will help you gain confidence and power in any face-to-face interaction. You should also start using your experience to train others and the effect of cultural differences on body language comprehension.*

Keywords: *non-verbal communication, body posture, gestures, facial expressions, social rejection, crucial to success.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ЯЗЫКА ТЕЛА В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В этой статье обсуждается использование языка тела на уроках английского языка и его значение, а также секрет невербального общения и полезные специальные стратегии, которые помогут вам обрести уверенность и силу в любом общении лицом к лицу. Вы также должны начать использовать свой опыт для обучения других и влияния культурных различий на понимание языка тела.*

Ключевые слова: *невербальная коммуникация, поза тела, жесты, мимика, социальное неприятие, решающее значение для успеха.*

INTRODUCTION

English language is an international language, that's why the requirements for having sufficient English language skills are improving. Communication skills are considered as the most focused skills because one must communicate fluently in order to succeed in professional interactions. All we know someone who can walk into a room full of people and within minutes give an accurate description about the relationships between those people and what they are feeling. The ability to read a person's attitudes and thoughts by their behavior was the original communication system used by humans before spoken language evolved. Our spoken language, however, recognizes how important body language is to our communication. A body language has a great role in any kind of interactions and professional interactions I chose the problem of the importance of non-verbal communication (body language) in teaching English.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Body language is a form of communication that doesn't involve any word, voice or writing and it consists of body posture, gestures, facial expressions, and eye movements. The process of communication which is done by body language is called Non-verbal communication in which messages can be communicated through gestures and touch, by body language or posture, by facial expression and eye contact, which are all considered types of non-verbal communication. While communicating humans send and interpret as much (even more than) non-verbal communication signals as the words we use.

Non-verbal language is used throughout society by both genders, in every culture and even in professional interactions. Some non-verbal communications are subconscious and the speaker doesn't or can't control them, while other non-verbal communication signals are special techniques which are used to help an audience follow the speaker's ideas, thoughts and feelings.

RESULTS

To begin to talk about the importance of non-verbal communication, let's pay attention to the fact that psychologists say that over 90% of all human communication is carried out with non-verbal signals and only 10% percent is verbal. In referring to communication, psychologists say that a person's impact depends seven percent on what is said, 38 percent on how it is said and, 55 percent on body language. Posture and stance, facial expressions, gestures, eye contact, proximity, and appearance all are the elements of body language. Most people do not realize just how much they use this unspoken language every time they communicate with another person. They use it unconsciously (Gordon, Wainwright: 10). Of course, the facts given above may be surprising for others. We also didn't agree with it first, but after some short investigations we realized that non-verbal communication skills are the main in the process of interaction.

DISCUSSION

Non-verbal language contributes very much to successful communication. Because non-verbal signals we send a lot. Non-verbal communication is a skill. In referring to communication, some people suffer from deficiencies so severe that they experience social rejection because of their poor non-verbal skills. And some demonstrate such an unusually high proficiency in non-verbal skills that they almost always excel in social interactions. Imagine that a person is being interviewed by the director of a company that he has applied for a job. First impression that the director will get from him is the appearance of his, from his style of dressing to the way he shake his hand will give a great impact on next things that he will say during conversation. Next, while he is conversing with him, he will be judged according to how he behave his voice, posture and gestures. His eye contact will show his attitude to his speech and also it helps to keep the listener's attention.

While over 90% of all human communication is non-verbal, some research suggests that at least 75% of all classroom communication is non-verbal. It makes sense therefore for teachers to use non-verbal communication to their advantage in the classroom. Body language is very important in teaching English as a foreign language. Unfortunately, non-verbal communication skills aren't taught in any educational institutions, but are crucial to success in professional and social settings. In academic lyceums and high educational institutions students are mainly taught the language itself, regardless the fact that culture is the key in learning any foreign language. Every student will need to be proficient in their body language in order to succeed in their future professional life. As we learn a foreign language with the aim of being able to interact with people from foreign countries, it is essential to learn the nations' cultural peculiarities, traditions, customs and also body language etiquette. Some non-verbal language elements may be general in every culture with the same meaning and some may differ from culture to culture. These differences in those non-verbal signals and being unaware of the dissimilar meaning of same non-verbal signals may lead to misunderstandings between people.

CONCLUSIONS

Having found out that body language is such an essential part of our communication, I think it is obligatory to take into account the importance of body language while teaching process. Also it is high time to investigate the non-verbal communication skills as one of the tools in teaching Foreign languages.

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